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The Revealed Comparative Advantage of Swaziland

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

The authors investigate the revealed comparative advantage of Swaziland. They investigate whether or not Swaziland has comparative advantage in the products it exports to the Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA), Southern African Development Community (SADC), Southern Africa Customs Union (SACU) and the rest of the world. The results show that Swaziland has $RCA \geq 1$ in 449 product lines hence has comparative advantage in such product lines. Chem wood pulp, sulphite, coniferous unbleached has the highest RCA index of 3106. The products in which Swaziland has comparative advantage includes manufactured and agricultural products. Swaziland could improve the range of the products in which it has comparative advantage through attracting foreign direct investment via transnational corporations and exploration of new resources.

Keywords: Comparative advantage, international trade, exports.

ABBREVIATIONS: Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA), Southern African Development Community (SADC), Southern Africa Customs Union (SACU).

INTRODUCTION

Swaziland is a member of COMESA. It is also a member of SADC and SACU. As a member of several regional groupings which have even established a customs union (CU) with a common external tariff (CET), Swaziland enjoys privileges associated with such regional groupings. The purpose of this paper is to investigate whether or not Swaziland has comparative advantage in the products it exports to COMESA, SADC, SACU and to the rest of the world.

Common Market For Eastern And Southern Africa (COMESA)

The Heads of State and Government on 7-8 June 2009 launched the COMESA customs union. The customs union is aimed at providing harmonized policies that would usher in more coherent integrated group. The member states of COMESA in pursuant of Article 47 of the Treaty agreed to a gradual establishment of a common external tariff which will be imposed on non-COMESA imported products. This would be imposed within ten years of establishing a customs union (COMESA, 2009).

Southern Africa Customs Union (SACU)

SACU was formed in 1910. Initially the arrangement involved levying duties on domestic production and then levying duties on imports of SACU member states coming from outside the customs union (SACU, 2012). According to the Southern African Institute of International Affairs (2011), there has been a decrease in funds to Botswana, Lesotho, Namibia and Swaziland from SACU revenue pool. The benefits which accrue to SACU member states are computed using three components. These are customs, excise and development. However, this paper's focus is not focusing on benefits and how they are shared. One of the goals of the 2002 SACU Agreement is to promote integration within the customs union into a global economy (SACU, 2012). Swaziland is an active participant in SACU activities. SACU has entered a number of trade agreements with other regional groupings such as the European Free Trade Association (EFTA).

Southern African Development Community (SADC)

SADC was formed in 1980 by nine majority-ruled States in Southern Africa. Initially, it was known as the Southern African Development Coordination Conference (SADCC). The overall goal of SADC trade protocol was to establish a Free Trade Area which would lead to the establishment of a customs union and eventually establishment of a common market. The goals of SADC trade policies are aimed at removing obstacles to free movement of capital, labour and goods and services and the improvement of the region's economic management through regional integration with the eventual goal of reducing the incidences of poverty (SADC, 2012). Swaziland is a member and active participant of SADC activities.

COMESA – EAC – SADC TRIPARTITE FREE TRADE AGREEMENT

The COMESA-EAC-SADC Free Trade Agreement was launched on 12 June 2011. The areas of cooperation include infrastructure development, industrial development and market (Trade Marks of Southern Africa, 2013). It was launched against the background that some member states belong to at least two of these organizations. The areas of duplication of activities are so evident, for example, Swaziland is a member of both COMESA and SADC and the two organizations are basically doing the same things.

COMPARATIVE ADVANTAGE

According to Case and Fair (2002), Ricardo's theory of comparative advantage addresses the issues of specialization and free trade. Two countries which engage in international trade will tend to benefit even though one of the countries may not have an absolute efficiency in producing any of the two products while the other trading country may have absolute advantage in the production of the two products. Beneficial trade occurs as long as opportunity costs differ and there is comparative advantage in a specific product by each of the countries. Ricardo focused on specialization and trade which would provide mutual benefits to both countries. When countries specialize in the production of goods in which they possess comparative advantage or competitive advantage, they are definitely going to optimize their combined output and allocate their combined endowment with great efficiency.

Hescheker –Ohlin extended Ricardo's theory of comparative advantage in the H-O theory. According to the H-O theory, comparative advantage comes from international differences in cost as a result of differences in factor endowment. A nation with a particular factor endowment, will export the product which uses such an abundant factor most intensively. It is then expected to import goods that use its scarce factor (Mzumara, 2006). Hescheker-Ohlin emphasized that the source of comparative advantage originates from factor endowment the nations possess (Widgren, 2005). However, Khatibi (2008) emphasizes on factor scarcity as the driver of comparative advantage.

Empirical Evidence Of Revealed Comparative Advantage

Yeats (1997) used RCA and concluded that Mercosur has no comparative advantage in the products it exports. The study also concluded that Mercosur's own trade restrictions determine trade variations. Mirzaei et al (2004) found that Iran has no comparative advantage in the eggs it exports to the Middle East region. Utkula and Seymen (2004) concluded there would be a possibility of negative trade creation effect for Turkey in the event of it joining the European Union. Trade diversion effects were not significant. Mutambatsere (2007) observed that half of SADC member countries did not have comparative advantage in the production of maize (corn). Only Malawi, South Africa and Tanzania had a comparative advantage in the production of maize (corn). Shinyekwa and Othieno (2011) found that Uganda has comparative advantage in a very limited range of products. Mzumara (2011a) concluded that Zimbabwe has comparative advantage in the production of a wide range of products. Mzumara (2011b) found Mozambique to have comparative advantage in the production of 222 product lines.

This explanation in essence is a departure from what Widgren (2005) and Mzumara (2006) concur that comparative advantage occurs from factor abundance in that a country that has an abundant factor will possess the comparative advantage in the production of a product that uses such a factor hence it is not a scarcity that leads a particular country to possess comparative advantage. Scarcity of factor endowment simply brings in comparative disadvantage rather than comparative advantage. According to Goldin (1990) a country has a comparative advantage in the production of a specific good if it has an endowment of factor used to produce it and that such a factor is used more intensively. This proposition in social sciences remains true and non-trivial. This has come to be considered as a universal law in international trade.

METHODOLOGY

The authors have used Balassa (1965) method in this paper. According to Wu and Chen (2004) Balassa's technique is useful in a dynamic competitive market economy. Comparative advantage as demonstrated in export composition is in line with comparative advantage based on a country's economy factor endowment and moves along with economic development.

The Balassa (1965) method is as follows:

$$RCA = \left(\frac{X_{i,j}}{X_{w,j}} \right) / \left(\frac{X_{i,tot}}{X_{w,tot}} \right)$$

With:

RCA denoting Revealed Comparative Advantage;

$X_{i,j}$ denoting country i 's exports value of product j ;

$X_{i,tot}$ denoting country i 's total exports value;

$X_{w,j}$ denoting the world's (all countries) export value of product j ; and

$X_{w,tot}$ denoting total exports value in the world.

An RCA of equal and greater than 1 demonstrates that the country has Revealed Comparative Advantage. In other words, the exporting nation is relatively specialized in producing and exporting the product line under consideration. An RCA of less than 1 demonstrates that a country has no Revealed Comparative Advantage and is not specialized in the product line (Balassa, 1965; Krugell & Matthee, 2009).

Data on exports for Swaziland and for the world was obtained from International Trade Centre (ITC)'s Trademap based in Geneva, Switzerland for 2008, 2009 and 2010. The data is a mirror data meaning it was not submitted by Swaziland instead ITC obtained it from other sources. An RCA was computed for every product separately for 2008, 2009 and 2010 then an average RCA for the three years was computed which was used either to reject as lack of comparative advantage or accepting that Swaziland possesses a comparative advantage in a particular product.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Swaziland was found to have an $RCA \geq 1$ in 449 products lines. This shows that Swaziland has revealed comparative advantage in those product lines hence is specialized in their production. Table 1 shows top 50 products with the highest RCA.

Table 1: Top 50 product with highest RCA in Swaziland

Product code	Product description	RCA 2008	RCA 2009	RCA 2010	Average RCA
470411	Chem wood pulp, sulphite, coniferous unbleached	2900.105	5792.385	626.3015	3106.264
410130	Bovine hides, raw	0	8772.334	0	2924.11
470319	Chem wood pulp, soda/sulphate	3839.222	707.8566	3.112915	1516.731
930529	Parts and accessories of shot guns or rifles	586.5158	586.5158	790.7367	654.5894
846930	Type writers, non-electric	0	0	1792.347	597.449
470311	Chem wood pulp, soda, sulphate, conifer, unbleached	621.0345	627.654	118.451	455.7131
290351	1,2,3,4,5,6-hexachlorocyclohexane	916.9687	0	0	305.6562

200830	Citrus fruits, otherwise prepared or preserved	248.9047	224.8994	222.5194	232.1078
080540	Grapefruit, fresh or dried	272.8298	184.4697	236.2399	231.1798
170111	Raw, sugar cane	2549911	238.3976	171.4902	221.6263
681130	Tube, pipes of asbestos or cellulose fibre cement	33.68037	538.886	0	190.8555
630641	Pneumatic mattresses, of cotton	0	0	556.2457	185.4152
681250	Asbestos clothing, accessories, foot and headwear	506.1747	0	0	168.7249
330210	Mixed odoriferous substances-food & drink industries	144.5833	133.6991	182.3594	153.5473
293341	Levonphanol and its salt	388.2518	0	0	129.4173
200929	Grapefruit juice, unfermented without added spirits	100.6744	100.9357	133.9253	111.8451
010639	Live birds	313.61	0	0	104.5363
840220	Super-heated water boilers	0	295.1137	0	98.37125
620722	Men's/boys nightshirts, pajama, manmade fibre, not knitted	149.7848	87.82347	53.21050	96.93951
847110	Analogue or hybrid computers	280.5135	2.125102	3.613603	95.41741
200791	Citrus based jams jellies marmalade	100.5206	75.68404	109.8005	95.33839
681190	Articles of asbestos or cellulose fibre cement	0	0	238.7438	79.58128
480429	Paper, sack kraft other than unbleached, uncoated	229.9813	0	0	76.6604
901540	Photogrammetrical surveying instruments, appliances	143.8385	70.51157	0	71.45001
960711	Slide fasteners with chain scoops of base metal	87.30381	45.32631	75.12528	69.2518
283719	Cyanides and cyanide oxides of metals except sodium.	207.4701	0	0	69.1567
200949	Pineapple juice, unfermented not containing added spirits	43.42892	67.57981	72.68278	61.23051
170199	Refined sugar, in solid form, pure sucrose	72.59165	66.74018	42.36817	60.5567
210690	Food preparations	56.52443	58.54027	65.57329	60.21267
080510	Oranges, fresh or dried	105.1064	38.78545	36.50533	60.13241
060310	Cut flowers and flowerbuds for bouquets, etc, fresh	177.3854	0	0	59.12846
200820	Pineapples, otherwise, prepared or preserved	57.1509	54.85666	62.87406	58.29387

841891	Furniture to take refrigerating/freezing equipment	49.65512	113.9476	0	54.53425
540262	Yarn of polyester filament, multiple, not retail	71.47353	31.25555	58.90493	53.878
200892	Fruit mixtures, otherwise prepared or preserved	69.29784	34.69441	46.46854	50.1536
470620	Pulp of fibres derived	0	149.3258	0	49.77525
911180	Watch cases	108.5516	9.789802	29.94297	49.42813
843780	Machines to mill or work cereals or dried legumes	132.4832	0.169368	0.037107	44.22988
610463	Women's, girls trousers, shorts synthetic fibres	49.52641	41.87149	34.93893	42.22175
910112	Wrist watch, precious metal, battery, electric	0	123.9906	0	41.3302
620463	Women's, girls trousers, shorts, synth fibres not knit	42.42999	32.97976	48.25549	41.22175
910620	Parking meters	0	108.9731	0	37.32437
902121	Artificial teeth	34.72941	34.72941	35.60985	35.02289
220710	Undenatured ethyl alcohol >80% by volume	42.88264	28.73064	32.66541	34.75956
910119	Wrist-watch precious metal, battery, other	4.210869	67.37391	30.82324	34.13601
382550	Wastes of metal pickling liquors	102.2086	0	0	34.06952
610230	Women's, girls overcoats, etc, manmade fibre, knitted	31.53728	28.070014	42.12763	33.91168
200840	Pears, otherwise prepared or preserved	45.27814	30.92003	24.76015	33.65277
290490	Hydrocarbon derives, mixed, sulpho/nitro/nitrose groups	98.36089	0	0	32.78696
930599	Parts & accessories of articles of 93.10-93.04	0	0	fr95.47356	31.82452

Source: Computed from the data obtained from Trademap (2013).

Chem wood pulp, coniferous unbleached has the highest index of 3106 followed by bovine hides with an index of 2924. The third position is occupied by chem. Wood pulp, soda/sulphate with an index of 15717. The fourth position is occupied by parts and accessories with an index 655. The fifth position is occupied by type writers with an index of 597.

The products in which Swaziland has comparative advantage include manufactured products and agricultural products. With 449 products in which Swaziland has comparative advantage, it is benefiting in engaging in international trade with other countries. Ricardo indicated in his theorem that only comparative advantage is necessary for a country to gain from international trade and that a country will always have some products in which it has comparative advantage. This is very consistent with the result here that Swaziland has comparative advantage in at least 449 product lines. The results are also consistent with earlier findings of empirical studies such as those done by Shinyekwa and Othieno (2011) and Mzumara (2011a, 2011b).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper concludes that Swaziland has 449 product lines in which it has revealed comparative advantage since the RCA index is greater than 1. Swaziland therefore has comparative advantage in such products. The products in which Swaziland has comparative advantage include manufactured products and agricultural products. It is recommended that Swaziland improves on the range of products that it has comparative advantage in. This can be achieved through further investment via foreign direct investment (FDI). FDI mainly by transnational corporations can bring in Swaziland technology and superior managerial skills which can help Swaziland have comparative advantage in other products also and improve its terms of trade. It is therefore recommended that Swaziland should work towards attracting such investment. Further it is recommended that the country do some exploration for a possible new resources discovery.

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